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JIS

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

Vision

“ENRICHING BEAUTIFUL MINDS TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS”

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) aims to disseminate scholarly research articles and papers to the wider community with the aim of offering an academic and scientific platform that provides an outlet to authors. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access online journal. Initially, the JIS will provide an online version, but is planning a print version later in this academic journey. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) focuses on a high-quality academic research articles and papers. All categories of research are of interest to the JIS, including insightful empirical studies, conceptual papers, commentary, essays, and theoretical articles.

JIS is an interdisciplinary platform and invites authors, academics, students, researchers, leaders, managers, scientists for their contributions in the disciplines of sciences, sociology, education, philosophy, humanities and management. Articles and Papers of scientific and academic rigour in Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed or Blend methods are welcome.

JIS intends to publish two issues per annum (May and November).

Submissions to, and Publication in, the JIS is free.

All papers submitted for publication will be peer reviewed.

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

mission is to “Guide Beautiful Minds towards Intellectual Enrichment”

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Editorial

Dear Readers,

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) wishes to announce the publication of Volume 7, Issue 1 (May 2023). In this issue, papers are included within the areas of social sciences, technologies, languages, economic - political Science, and health education.

Our next issue will be published in November 2023 we invite researchers, managers, leaders, scientists, students and others for paper submission. The call for paper submission is also announced in the journal's announcement portal

<http://journalofinterdisciplinarysciences.com/announcement/>

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an online open access journal, which offers free submissions, free publication and open access to download its published research paper from the journal's website <http://journalofinterdisciplinarysciences.com/>

It is recommended that all author(s) submitting their manuscript to JIS are advised to read the author guidelines from the journal website

<http://journalofinterdisciplinarysciences.com/submit-your-papers/authors-guidelines/>

Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS**

Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari. Ph.D.
Founder and Editor-in-Chief
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